

Transformative Change Assessment Directory

This page is designed to help navigate through all the documents of the transformative change assessment, such as the data management reports, figures and all accompanying documents.

Table of contents

Full report	3
Summary for policymakers	3
Chapter 1. Transformative change and a sustainable world	3
Chapter 2. Visions of a sustainable world – for nature and people	3
Chapter 3. How transformative change occurs	3
Chapter 4. Overcoming the challenges of achieving transformative change to- wards a sustainable world	4
Chapter 5. Realizing a sustainable world for nature and people: transformative strategies, actions and roles for all	4
Glossary	4
Underlying bibliographic data and research materials	4
Linked Open Data	5

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Full report

- Full report
- Data management report on the case studies database with transformative potential and pitfalls
- Transformative Change assessment Corpus
- Data management report on the Corpus of literature on transformative change

Summary for policymakers

- SPM
- The figures, tables and captions used in the SPM
- Translations of the SPM in Arabic, Chinese, French, Russian and Spanish

Chapter 1. Transformative change and a sustainable world

- Chapter 1
- Figures, tables and captions
- Data management report 1.1 Analysis of effectiveness of environmental governance
- Data management report 1.2 Analysis of contributions on what transformative change is according to different communities of knowledge
- Data management report 1.3 Literature and data review regarding the underlying causes of biodiversity loss
- Data management report 1.4 Literature review determining the principles of transformative change
- Evidence causes data - data package
- Analysis of knowledge gaps

Chapter 2. Visions of a sustainable world – for nature and people

- Chapter 2
- Figures, tables, captions and data management reports

Chapter 3. How transformative change occurs

- Chapter 3
- Figures, tables and captions
- Data Management Report 3.1 Review of knowledge on theories and frameworks of transformative change

- [Data Management Report 3.2 Systematic review of literature on transformative change for sustainability](#)
- [Data Management Report 3.3 Identification of on-going initiatives with transformative potential](#)

Chapter 4. Overcoming the challenges of achieving transformative change towards a sustainable world

- [Chapter 4](#)
- [Figures, tables and captions](#)
- [Data Management Report 4.1 Review of literature on persistent and pervasive relations of domination forged in colonial eras](#)
- [Data Management Report 4.2 Review of literature on power imbalances and inequalities](#)
- [Data Management Report 4.3 Review of literature on institutional misfits and inadequate policies](#)
- [Data Management Report 4.4 Review of literature on unsustainable consumption and production patterns and individual habits and practices](#)
- [Data Management Report 4.5 Review of literature on limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems](#)

Chapter 5. Realizing a sustainable world for nature and people: transformative strategies, actions and roles for all

- [Chapter 5](#)
- [Figures, tables and captions](#)
- [Data Management Report 5.1. Instruments, actions and strategies for transformative change](#)
- [Data Management Report 5.2 Literature review on harmful subsidies](#)
- [Data Management Report 5.3 Analysis of civil society initiatives](#)
- [Data Management Report 5.4 Literature review on governance](#)

Glossary

- [TCA glossary](#)

Underlying bibliographic data and research materials

- [TCA Zotero library](#)

Linked Open Data

- [Transformative Change Assessment in Linked Open Data](#)